

A Hospital-Based Retrospective Cross-Sectional Study on Adherence of Animal Bite Victims to Anti-Rabies Vaccine in A Tertiary Care Hospital in Assam

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Abstract:

Background: This retrospective cross-sectional research aims to assess the degree of adherence to ARV regimens among victims of animal bites, identify socio-demographic characteristics related with adherence, and investigate the role of healthcare personnel in impacting patient adherence. The study was conducted in a hospital setting.

Aim: The purpose of this study was to ascertain the degree to which victims of animal bites adhered to the Anti-Rabies Vaccine ARV regimen and to describe the type of exposure present among animal bite patients.

Materials & Methods: In Assam, the Lakhimpur Medical College and Hospital may be found in North Lakhimpur. The ARV section of the LMCH Central Pharmacy, which uses a systematic approach to monitor patients and their medicines, provided us with the information we gathered throughout our investigation. A total of six months were spent doing the research, beginning on July 1, 2023 and ending on December 31, 2023. This study utilized a retrospective cross-sectional design, and the data was taken from hospital records.

Results: A significant number of participants were bitten by an animal (n = 259, 95% confidence interval: 52–62%) than scratched by an animal (n = 185, 95% confidence interval: 37–46%), the most prevalent kind of attacker was a dog (51%, n = 230, 95% confidence interval: 45–55%), followed by a cat (43-52%). Majority of the victims were male of age group 18-30 years. Most of the patients received intradermal regime of vaccination while 22% preferred intramuscular regime. During the course of the research, a total of 192 individuals were given rabies immunoglobulin with the initial dose of the post-exposure vaccination. 379 out of 450 patients completed the full course of vaccination., Most received the vaccination within 24 hours while in 18.6 % the vaccination was administered between the first and third day, with 54 individuals citing other obligations as the reason for the deferral.

Conclusion: High rabies PEP compliance was discovered in the study, which may be attributed to victims' knowledge and the availability of free vaccination. However, delay in 1st dose, default and Nonadherence to vaccine schedule has come to light. To provide adequate protection of PEP, addressing difficulties and being aware of potential impediments is essential.

Keywords: Anti-rabies vaccination, Immunoglobulins, Dog, Cat, Scratch, Bite, Licks, Post-exposure prophylaxis.

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Introduction

When it comes to infectious illnesses, rabies was one of the first to be identified. This viral infection,

which causes encephalomyelitis, is linked with a 100% mortality rate [1]. Rabies may infect any

species, including humans, wild dogs, domestic cats, bobcats, lions, skunks, badgers, monkeys, bats, wolves, and coyotes. Although all animals may get rabies, it strikes land animals and birds the worst. The canine is and always has been the primary vector for rabies transmission. [1-7]. These findings are consistent with historical data. Rabies is a significant public health problem all over the world since it is responsible for around 59,000 fatalities each year [8]. Adherence to anti-rabies vaccinations (ARVs) remains a concern [9]. However, these vaccines are essential for post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP). Several factors might impact adherence, including socioeconomic restraints, ignorance, cultural beliefs, and healthcare facilities [6]. Tertiary care facilities, which provide a broad patient population, are the key source of referrals for the subject under investigation.

Non-adherence to anti-rabies vaccinations (ARV) can reduce the effectiveness of preventative medication and increase the risk of rabies. Considerations such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, level of education, proximity to healthcare resources, and the nature of the animal attack are among the factors influencing adherence [10]. The need to adhere to the ARV schedule is something that patients are taught by healthcare experts, who play a critical part in this process. Rabies in dogs is a severe problem affecting the national economy and public health. It is estimated that the illness takes the lives of 59,000 individuals per year, the majority of whom are located in underserved countries in Africa and Asia [11].

There are more than 150 countries and regions where the rabies virus may be found [7-9]. It has been recognized as one of the most prominent zoonotic illnesses in India since the Vedic time [3]. Because it mostly affects economically disadvantaged populations, tropical diseases like rabies are generally disregarded [6]. So, this research set out to examine the types of exposure experienced by people who had been bitten by animals and to see out how well they followed the Anti-Rabies Vaccine ARV schedule.

Materials & Methods

In Assam, the Lakhimpur Medical College and Hospital may be found in North Lakhimpur. The ARV section of the LMCH Central Pharmacy,

which uses a systematic approach to monitor patients and their medicines, provided us with the information we gathered throughout our investigation. A total of six months were spent doing the research, beginning on July 1, 2023 and ending on December 31, 2023. This study utilized a retrospective cross-sectional approach, and the data was collected from hospital records.

The Anti-Rabies Vaccine Register and the Post Exposure Prophylaxis Card provided by the central pharmacy served as the materials we used as references. Participants in the trial included anyone who expressed interest in receiving the anti-rabies vaccination between July 1 and December 31.

For participants to be eligible for post exposure prophylaxis (PEP), they were required to have started taking ARV with a zero-day dosage at LMCH to begin the treatment. Participants, who transferred to LMCH from another centre where they got ARV medication, as well as those who use ARV for pre- or re-exposure prophylaxis, were not granted permission to take part in the study.

A sample size of 450 is necessary, according to data previously published from studies carried out in different regions of India (8, 9). This is based on the assumption that there is a dropout rate of 10%, an absolute precision of 5%, and a compliance rate of 50% with the ARV. Daily, there are around 17–20 instances of animal bites that necessitate anti-rabies vaccination and an average of 5 to 7 patients at LMCH report that they require their initial dose of ARV. The random number generator available in Microsoft Excel to select the participants of the study. Data on participants' age, gender, exposure date, bite sites, exposure category, animal type, ARV administration route (intramuscular or intravenous), and AR immunoglobulins received or not received were collected. Vaccination dates for 0–3–7–14–28 days for intramuscular regimens and 0–3–7–28 days for intradermal regimens were included in the study's parameters.

Statistical analysis: Microsoft Excel 2021 was utilized to enter the information gathered from the registers. We cleaned and confirmed the information that was entered. To do our descriptive analysis, we used SPSS Version 23. A percentage breakdown and a frequency distribution were shown for the results.

Results

Table 1: Age & gender of the study population (n=450)

Male	319	65–75%
Female	131	26–32%
Age		
1–5 years	36	6–11%
6–10 years	54	9–15%
11–17 years	68	13–19%

18–30 years	144	29–36%
31–50 years	112	21–29%
> 50 years	36	6–11%

The research included 450 individuals of WHO category II and III exposure to animals at some point of time. All individuals who participated in the research project were predominantly male, with an average age of 28 years (standard deviation $\pm$ 17.8) and a range of ages spanning from 1 to 65 years. Most of them were within the age range of 18 to 30 years.

Table 2: Level of education of the study population (n=450)

Education		
Illiterate	59	10–16%
Primary level	99	19–25%
Secondary level	153	30–38%
Higher secondary level	72	14–20%
Graduate level	67	11–17%

Table 3: Site of bite in the study population (n=450)

Site of bites/scratches/lick		
Upper limb	165	34–41%
Lower limb	237	50–56%
Head	5	1–3%
Face	14	1–6%
Neck	5	1–2%
Trunk	14	2–6%
Other sites	5	1–3%
Multiple sites	5	1–3%

Table 4: Category of exposure

Types of animal exposure		
Animal bite	259	52–62%
Animal scratch	185	37–46%
Animal licking	6	1–3%

Regarding type of exposure a significant number of participants were bitten by an animal (n = 259, 95% confidence interval: 52–62%) than scratched by an animal (n = 185, 95% confidence interval: 37–46%) (Table 4). As expected the lower limbs followed by upper limbs are the most common sites of exposure together accounting for 90% of all ex-

posures. According to the data in Table 5, the most prevalent kind of attacker was a dog (51%, n = 230, 95% confidence interval: 45–55%), followed by a cat (43–52%). A significant number of animals (n = 237, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 50–56%) and a subset of animals (n = 165, 95% CI: 34–41%) exhibited symptoms of exposure.

Table 5: Type of animal bite in the study population (n=450)

Species of animals who bit participant		
Dog	230	45–55%
Cat	211	43–52%
Monkey	3	1–2%
Other animals (mongoose/rat/horse/ fox)	6	1–3%

Table 5: Characteristics of PEP of Anti-rabies vaccine or Anti-rabies immunoglobulins

Received first dose of rabies vaccine	450			-
Received rabies immunoglobulin	192			39–46%
Recommended vaccine doses by physician				
Four doses (day 0/day 3/day 7/ day 28) ID	351			74–82%
Four doses (day 0/day 3/day 7/ day 14/ day 28) IM	99			18–28%
	ID	IM	Total	
Received dose 1	351	99	450	-

Received dose 2	345	96	441	95–99%
Received dose 3	334	89	423	92–96%
Received dose 4	310	74	384	80–88%
Received dose 5 (IM regime only)		69	69	
Complete vaccination according to a recommendation				
Completed all doses (4 in ID regime & 5 in IM regime)	310 +69 = 379			
Received a total of three doses (n = 423)	423			-
Received a total of 4 doses (n = 384)	384			79–88%
Did not complete (n = 66)	66 71			12–18%
Vaccine received on an actual recommended day.				
Completed course appropriately (n = 379)	374			80–88%
Completed course but not appropriately (n = 379)	5			1–6%
Received three doses ID four doses IM appropriately (n = 423)	404			90–95%
Received three doses but not appropriately (n = 423)	4			1–3%

On the day participants were recruited, rabies immunoglobulin was given to 192 (95% confidence interval: 39-46%). The first dose of the post-exposure vaccination was given to all 450. All participants were instructed to undertake either a four-dose intradermal regimen or five dose intramuscular vaccine within the first one month of the exposure. Of the 450 people enrolled in the study, 384 successfully received the full immunization. A total of 351 patients were prescribed intradermal regime of ARV and 99 patients were prescribed intramuscular regime of ARV. In the intradermal group 310 out of 351 patients completed the course while in intramuscular group 69 out of 99 patients completed the course. As a result of the bite or scratch, 366 of the 450 persons received the post-exposure vaccination on the same day. The vaccination was administered to some subjects (n = 84,) often between the first and third day following the bite or scratch. Of those who took part in the survey, 54 said they had to wait until they had other commitments to get their vaccination

Discussion:

Administering rabies vaccine with or without immunoglobulin, known as rabies post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP), is the most efficient way to reduce rabies-related deaths. Administering PEP correctly and at the correct time following exposure is crucial for its efficacy [14]. Our study included looking at rabies compliance after exposure. Nearly eighty-eight percent to ninety-five percent of animal bite patients finished the full course of vaccination. Vaccinations were administered to almost 90% of victims in accordance with the hospital's PEP procedure. In comparison to other resource-constrained nations, the immunization completion rate is substantially higher [7,9,10]. Patients were far more likely to adhere to the PEP regimen, with 98% finishing the second dosage as prescribed, 94% finishing the third dose as scheduled, 88% finishing the fourth dose as planned, and 82% finishing the fifth dose as scheduled. While 88% of the patients completed the full course of ARV, it was found that many patients did not adhere to the

dates strictly. To achieve the aim of eliminating human mortality caused by dog-mediated rabies by the year 2030, it is crucial that individuals stick to the PEP that the government advises.

Ignorance of the disease, socioeconomic status or remoteness may have contributed to a non-completion of PEP in some participants. In our region, government hospitals offer free rabies vaccines and AR immunoglobulins, which may encourage people to finish their PEP programs. Sometimes they had to spend a very modest amount of money to purchase medications related to wound care. According to the findings of a study [9], low adherence may result from prevailing folklore and magic remedial practices prevalent among certain population groups. This study discovered that a tiny percentage of people did not receive the immunization promptly. According to the conclusions of this study, there are a few particular causes for delayed vaccination. These reasons include a lack of understanding about early immunization, a reluctance to obtain the vaccine, and distance.

The risk of contracting rabies was highest among adults and young individuals, according to our findings. However, research done in 2020 found that most of the deaths in Bangladesh were of those younger than 20 or infants [1, 10]. Our data shows that most of the impacted individuals middle aged adult males with at least an elementary education and had finished secondary school.

The majority of the people who took part in our research were attacked by healthy animals, with the majority of the attacks focusing on the lower limbs of the individuals (54%)—a previous body of research on rabies exposure in comparable outputs [8, 9,11]. According to a study's findings, most wounds tended to be located on the Lower limbs (54%). In addition, our investigation findings demonstrated that most patients (71%) cleansed the area around the wound (12%) with soap and water. In contrast, many patients did not take any more steps to address their injuries.

According to previous research [10], most sufferers contact traditional healers rather than seek primary animal bite care. It came as a surprise to us when our study revealed that a tiny percentage of victims went to traditional healers rather than seeking primary animal bite care.

An additional crucial aspect of PEP is the timely administration of rabies vaccines. It appears that there is some lack of concern about rabies post-exposure immunization, since out of 450 participants only 366 victims got the vaccine on the day of exposure, while the remaining 84 who got it on days 1-3. Given that the vaccination was given no more than three days after exposure, this proved to be the case. Most people who were potentially exposed to the virus got the vaccination within the first three days. However, a much higher-than-average percentage of patients who received the vaccine on the same day they were exposed to an animal bite were found in different research [12]. If the first dose of vaccine wasn't received on the day of exposure, it may be because the person wasn't aware of or didn't fully grasp the risks of postponing vaccination. Victims of animal bite have shown ignorance about the recommended vaccination schedule. The distance between their residence and the hospital was mentioned by participants as one of the most prevalent causes.

A few restrictions were placed on this investigation. This hospital research is unable to evaluate the levels of PEP compliance and adherence between high-risk groups (those whose rabid animals bite) and low-risk groups (those whose rabid animals did not bite). There is a possibility that the findings that we are showing only represent a nominal portion of the total number of occurrences in our region. Some factors may be responsible for the high level of vaccine compliance among individuals living in this region. These factors include free vaccination, moderate to high level of literacy, a better transportation system, a more significant income, more accessible access to hospitals, and increased awareness.

Conclusion

In the population under research, there was significant compliance with the PEP. A combination of the victims' high level of information and awareness and the provision of a free vaccination may result in improved adherence to the rabies prevention and treatment program. On the other hand, the vaccine's initial dosage was given to many patients between the first and third day of the exposure.

By drawing greater attention to the matter, we can reduce the number of days between the initial post-exposure vaccination and the animal attack to zero. For PEP to provide considerable protection, it is vital to have a more in-depth understanding of the

potential obstacles, blockages, and other connected difficulties. Factors which results in Nonadherence to vaccination schedule and factors that leads to default needs to be evaluated in more detail.

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